

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KOINA****FIRST NAME: ALLAITOM****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What elements should contain in the essay paragraph?

- Introduction, Development, Conclusion.
- A topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidences, analysis, and a critical conclusion.¹**
- Introduction, supporting sentences, analysis, and a conclusion.
- Introduction, hypothesis, evidences, and conclusion.

2. What kinds of questions should the researcher ask him/herself during academy paper?

- What should we think, what should we do, and what to do?²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 3.

² Kate L. Turabian, *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 16-17.

- How to convince the audience?
- How to formulate my topic sentence?
- All above.

3. **Why should the researcher cite his/her sources?**

- To give a credit to the author.**³
- To avoid jail time.
- To make his/her professor happy.
- All above.

4. **In general, what order of elements should be included in the sources?**

- First name, last name, title, and facts of publications.
- Last name, first name, facts of publications, and title.
- Last name, first name, title, and facts of publications.**⁴
- Last name, title, and facts of publications.

5. **In American English how should the quotation marks been written?**

- The quotation starts with inverted commas; the quotation within this quotation is in quotation marks.

³ Turabian, 86.

⁴ Ibid., 92.

The quotation starts with quotation marks; the quotation within this quotation is put in inverted commas.⁵

Inverted commas are used for both.

Quotation marks are used for both.

6. **What is the main objective for writing a dissertation?**

To provide information that will be broaden student understanding of what comprises a sound research study.⁶

Because it is required by his/her university.

To bring a solution to a problem.

To vehicle a message.

7. **In what case is the researcher not required to cite?**

When it is a common knowledge.⁷

When the paragraph is too long.

When the professor allows to do so.

When summarizing.

8. **Select a type of plagiarism student must avoid.**

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 35.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 1st edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008), 2.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 10.

- Using another writer's words without proper citation.**⁸
- Using the exact words of a source with a quotation marks or indentation.
- Using another writer's ideas with proper citation.
- None of above.
9. **According to Turabian Style, if there are many authors, how does the researcher record their names?**
- The researcher should record all the authors 'names.
- Only the first listed author's name is in inverted order; names of additional authors follow but are inverted.**⁹
- The research should record the full name of the first author follow by the rest of the authors 'last names.
- The research should record only the name of the first author.
10. **In the research paper, when is an information considered irrelevant?**
- When the information is anecdotal, and superlative.**¹⁰
- When the information comes from the primary source.
- When the information is common.
- When the information does not make any sense.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 24.

⁹ Turabian, 138-161.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 6-7.

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